

HARNESSING TERMITE DIGESTIVE CAPABILITIES FOR RENEWABLE BIOGAS PRODUCTION: A CONTROLLED STUDY WITH DIFFERENT CELLULOSIC FEEDSTOCKS

ADEKUNLE OYEWALE ALIU^{1*}, YEMISI AKINDURENI¹ AND NWOSE SEBASTIAN AZOWENU²

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria

²Department of Civil Engineering, Delta State Polytechnic, Ogwashi Uku, Delta State, Nigeria

Corresponding author e-mail: adekunleoyewale_aliu@rugipo.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The invasion of the human environment by termites, which is a significant threat to both material goods and human resources, has necessitated the need for a control measure. Termites constantly feasted on dried agricultural and wooden furniture, thereby destroying valuables. The termites, specifically *Macrotermes subhyalinus* species belonging to the Termitidae family within the order Isoptera, were harnessed and placed in an enclosed chamber (prototype shelter, made of transparent polycarbonate material) for biogas extraction at a temperature between 20 °C to 28 °C, at a relative humidity between 81 – 92%. The termites were fed daily with 0.5 kg of organic material (brown paper) and tested based on the consumed mass of carbon paper and the energy released after consumption daily for 15 days. Results showed that 0.3 to 0.69 kg of brown paper was consumed, with an average of 1902 cm³ to 3990 cm³ gas produced within 15 days, while the volume of gas produced using elephant grass was within the range of 2393 cm³ to 4250 cm³ for equivalent 0.33 to 0.59 kg of elephant grass consumed. A total of 68% and 66% methane was produced by elephant-fed and brown paper-fed termites, respectively, compared to other gases produced. The harnessing of this gas as a substitute cooking gas will improve living standards and reduce afforestation linked to firewood usage.

Keywords: termites, biogas, *Macrotermes subhyalinus*, brown paper, elephant grass

INTRODUCTION

Termites are a real threat to the agricultural system around the world. It is estimated that their damage cost more than 40 billion USD annually to the global economy. They damage crops, plantations, and forestry from sowing till harvesting, and their damage symptoms are not noticeable at an early stage (Ahmad *et al.*, 2021). There are over 2800 different species of termites that are known today, with 185 among them, classified as pests in agricultural areas and housing structures (Ghaly & Edwards, 2011). They are often referred to as "silent destroyers", but they also perform their roles in the ecosystem

by breaking down tough plant fibres and recycling dead wood and other cellulose-based materials (Zebiri *et al.*, 2024). The termites are usually attracted to waste papers and have the potential to convert and manage lignocellulosic waste (discarded paper) to produce biomass. Despite their attraction for lignocellulosic fibre, the termites are selective (not all lignocellulosic fibres are suitable for them) in their fibre decomposition (Lenz *et al.*, 2011).

Existing control of termites includes the use of poisonous chemicals or repellents, with the chemicals retained in the timber over a long period and non-corrosive to the wood itself (Ghaly & Edwards, 2011). Diba *et al.* (2022) illustrated another approach to termite control using waste paper as bait, treated with basil extract at a concentration of 1.2ml. The extract was drained for 5 minutes and applied at 2% concentration intervals, ranging from 2% to 10%, over 21 days. The study found that 8% was the optimal concentration of basil leaf extract, achieving 91.52% termite mortality while resulting in only 8.3% weight loss of the bait material.

Even though termites can be destructive, they are the most dominant arthropod decomposers with extraordinary ecological impact on both agricultural and non-agricultural ecosystems through their significant role in the global carbon cycle, decomposition process and mineralisation of nutrient-rich cellulose. They are beneficial in the improvement of soil fertility, water infiltration and crop yield (Ahmad *et al.*, 2021). Nkrumah *et al.* (2006) demonstrated that there is a significant association between residual feed intake and methane production and measures of metabolic rate and dietary energy partitioning in them. Muin and Arif (2017) described termites *Macrotermes sp.* as fond of utilising their food source, especially waste carbon paper, and converting it into valuable biogenic products, thereby enhancing the physical and chemical properties of soil.

The need to incorporate termites' advantage for the general populace shows that termite gut inoculum can produce methane gas, which is a more valuable and cleaner fossil fuel than coal and oil for households, and at the same time, renewable. According to Gupta *et al.* (2012), termites produced 39.98 cm³ in 49 days and an additional 45.32 cm³ in the following 42 days and a decline thereafter. For a control measure between termite activities and ecosystem balance, there is a need to develop methods of harnessing termites for biogas production, creating a sustainable ecosystem where these insects contribute to renewable energy generation rather than facing elimination. By designing specialised collection systems that capture termites and their waste products, households could benefit from small-scale biogas reactors that utilise the termites' efficient lignocellulose digestion capabilities while preserving their population for continued ecological functions.

This study aimed to harvest biogas from termites using two principal feed sources: brown paper and elephant grass. By providing these materials to termite colonies and monitoring their consumption, biogas produced was collected and measured in relation to the weight of feed consumed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used for this research include elephant grass and brown paper, a tetrahedron prototype mound with a cubic base (polycarbonate material), a 0-1-liter gas rotameter, a transparent hose, gas bags, and a temperature and humidity digital meter. The existing termite colony (*Macrotermes subhyalinus* species) was located in Akure, and the constructed prototype mound, as seen in Figure 1, was placed on the ground, close to the existing mound. The temperature of the termite colony was carefully monitored to ensure it was within 25°C – 32°C. The total surface area of the mound is 1.56 m², and a total volume of 0.167 m³. According to Nanda *et al.* (2018), the maximum boundary of termite population for 1000cm³ (0.001m³) is 590 individuals. Hence, a volume of 0.167 m³ is expected to accommodate 98,530 termites.

Figure 1: Prototype mound details

The experimental prototype, a controlled observation designed to facilitate visual monitoring of the termite behaviour, was embedded within an excavation made directly into the existing termite colony. This integration with the natural colony provides access to the termite population with enabled systematic observation. The feeding was conducted through the aperture opening in the prototype structure. Two distinct cellulose-based materials were tested as food sources: processed brown paper and harvested dried elephant grass. Each feeding material was moderately wetted with water and administered at a constant rate of 0.5 kg per day for 15 days, with separate trials for each material, as illustrated in

Figure 2. This protocol allowed a comparative analysis of consumption patterns, feeding preferences, and activity levels between the two cellulose sources.

A transparent hose was connected from the prototype to the rotameter and from the outlet of the rotameter to the collection bags. The control valve on the rotameter enables careful removal of the gas bag without allowing the escape of biogas. The prototype box enabled continuous access to visual assessment of the termite foraging behaviour, consumption rates and colony movements without disturbing the natural activity pattern.

Figure 2: Collection Process

The gas produced from the termites was extracted with the hose installed and measured using the rotameter flow meter (0 – 1 L/min). The control valve on the rotameter was used to regulate the gas collected. The generated gas was analysed using a Mass Spectrometry scan.

Biogas yield and assessment

The produced gas will be assessed based on the feeding weight, with a regression line to identify their relationship. A model will be developed based on their relationship for future predictions. The strength of this relationship will be identified using the coefficient of determination (R^2), which will indicate the percentage variation in gas production that a change in feeding weight can explain.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The observed temperature and humidity for the elephant grass-fed colony ranged between 28 °C to 30 °C and 80% to 92%, respectively.

Figure 3: Temperature for both substrates (Elephant grass and Brown paper fed)

Figure 4: Relative humidity for both substrates (Elephant grass and Brown paper fed)

As illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 4, The average temperature and humidity were 28.6 °C and 87.3% respectively. This observation is similar to findings by Ndlovu and Pérez-Rodríguez (2018) that the mound's internal temperature is within the range of (29 – 32°C) for optimal fungal growth. The cultivated symbiotic fungi, which is necessary for the digestion of lignin, require that termites maintain this temperature range of 29 and 32 °C (Joseph *et al.*, 2018). The temperature and humidity for the brown paper-fed colony ranged between 27.3 °C to 29 °C and 81% to 92%, respectively. The observed mean temperature and humidity for the brown paper-fed colony are 27.9 °C and 87.9%, respectively. This is similar to the findings by Joseph *et al.* (2018) for elephant-fed termites. The termites possess the ability to maintain a stable temperature and humidity within their colony, as observed. Despite the increase in temperature externally, the temperature within the colony was stable at the observed range of 27 – 29 °C all around (day and night). This thermal regulation and stable habitat behaviour was also observed by (Aiki *et al.*, 2019).

Humidity is not the only source of water that is available. Metabolic water obtained during the process of food breakdown, free liquid water and water bounds to various substrates account for sources of water in the colony (Zukowski & Su, 2017). Termites colonies produce a range of gases that potentially affects atmospheric or geological emissions (Bignell, 2010). The relationship between the food substrate and the gas produced, as illustrated in Figure 5, shows that there is more gas produced when elephant grass is supplied than when brown paper is fed to the termites.

Figure 5: Gas produced with different substrates

Figure 6: Weight of food consumed

However, from Figure 6, it can be observed that the termites consumed brown paper more than elephant grass. Although the enzymes and microorganisms cannot easily decompose the complex structure of this lignocellulose waste due to their poor fluidity (Gao *et al.*, 2022), the initial wetting before feeding helps to overcome this challenge. This is in line with the general observation that termites have a good taste demand for brown paper. Despite the higher consumption of brown paper in comparison with the elephant grass, the elephant grass produced a higher volume of gas (4250 cm³) than the volume of gas produced by brown paper (3990 cm³).

S/N	Gas Composition	Elephant Grass		Brown Paper	
		% Produced (Retention Time (min))	% Wt	% Produced (Retention Time (min))	% Wt
1	Hydrogen	4.00	0.91	4.00	0.27
2	Oxygen	11.62	0.26	9.75	0.16
3	Ethane	17.04	0.30	17.58	0.31
4	Propane	12.75	0.27	23.51	0.98
5	Methane	19.50	68.69	43.00	66.96
6	Ammonia	21.50	0.68	24.98	0.89
7	Carbon dioxide	23.75	23.32	17.00	25.38

8	Nitrogen	24.50	2.15	37.99	0.93
9	Water Vapour	26.50	0.21	26.98	0.78
10	Carbon monoxide	29.00	0.01	36.25	0.08
11	Hydrogen Sulphide	29.75	2.72	42.00	1.92
12	Sulphur Oxide	40.18	0.18	44.70	1.34

As demonstrated in Table 1, from the gas chromatography result, various gases were produced by the termites. Methane, which is the dominant gas generated, has a production quantity of 68.69, and 66.96 % generated by elephant grass-fed and brown paper-fed termites, respectively. Apart from methane gas, other primary gases produced include carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulphide and Nitrogen.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The possibility of harnessing biogas from termites has been researched, and the following conclusions can be drawn: The rate of feeding of termites is directly proportional to the volume of gas produced. The termites have a greater taste for brown paper than elephant grass. The volume of gas produced by elephant grass-fed termites is higher than that of brown paper-fed termites. Termites can regulate their colony temperature without being affected by external atmospheric conditions. The volume of methane gas produced by elephant grass (68%) is higher than that produced by brown paper-fed termites (66%). The use of termites for the production of biogas or cooking gas will reduce dependence on fossil fuels and reduce afforestation related to the use of wood for cooking in rural areas. Future research can investigate the process of thermal regulation of termite colonies and adopt the same technology for industrial or personal purposes. Future research can investigate gas produced by other termite' species that is different from

Macrotermes subhyalinus.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, F., Fouad, H., Liang, S. Y., Hu, Y., & Mo, J. C. (2021). Termites and Chinese agricultural system: applications and advances in integrated termite management and chemical control. *Insect science*, 28(1), 2-20.
- Aiki, I. P., Pirk, C. W. W., & Yusuf, A. A. (2019). Thermal regulatory mechanisms of termites from two different savannah ecosystems. *Journal of Thermal Biology*, 85, 102418.
- Bignell, D. E. (2010). Termites. In *Methane and climate change* (pp. 62-73). Routledge.

- Diba, F., Wiranata, P., Nurhaida, N., Dirhamsyah, M., & Hartono, R. (2022). Bio-Attractant of termites bait from waste paper and extract *Ocimum basilicum* Linn against Subterranean Termites *Coptotermes curvignathus* Holmgren. *Wood Research Journal*, *13*(2), 48-55.
- Gao, Z., Alshehri, K., Li, Y., Qian, H., Sapsford, D., Cleall, P., & Harbottle, M. (2022). Advances in biological techniques for sustainable lignocellulosic waste utilization in biogas production. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *170*, 112995. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112995>
- Ghaly, A., & Edwards, S. (2011). Termite damage to buildings: Nature of attacks and preventive construction methods. *Am. J. Eng. Appl. Sci*, *4*(2), 187-200.
- Gupta, P., Singh, R. S., Sachan, A., Vidyarthi, A. S., & Gupta, A. (2012). Study on biogas production by anaerobic digestion of garden-waste. *Fuel*, *95*, 495-498. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2011.11.006>
- Joseph, G. S., Seymour, C. L., Coetzee, B. W., Ndlovu, M., Deng, L., Fowler, K., Hagan, J., Brooks, B. J., Seminara, J. A., & Foord, S. H. (2018). Elephants, termites and mound thermoregulation in a progressively warmer world. *Landscape Ecology*, *33*, 731-742.
- Lenz, M., Lee, C.-Y., Lacey, M. J., Yoshimura, T., & Tsunoda, K. (2011). The Potential and Limits of Termites (Isoptera) as Decomposers of Waste Paper Products. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, *104*(1), 232-242. <https://doi.org/10.1603/ec10155>
- Muin, M., & Arif, A. (2017). Conversion of waste paper-based bait formulation for biogenic production by termites in tropical land. *The Journal of Solid Waste Technology and Management*, *43*(1), 75-81.
- Nanda, M., Seminar, K., Nandika, D., & Maddu, A. (2018). Population survey of subterranean termite *Coptotermes curvignathus* (Isoptera: Rhinotermitidae) on infested pine boards.
- Ndlovu, M., & Pérez-Rodríguez, A. (2018). Temperature fluctuations inside savanna termite mounds: Do size and plant shade matter? *Journal of Thermal Biology*, *74*, 23-28. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtherbio.2018.03.004>
- Nkrumah, J. D., Okine, E. K., Mathison, G. W., Schmid, K., Li, C., Basarab, J. A., Price, M. A., Wang, Z., & Moore, S. S. (2006). Relationships of feedlot feed efficiency, performance, and feeding behavior with metabolic rate, methane production, and energy partitioning in beef cattle1. *Journal of Animal Science*, *84*(1), 145-153. <https://doi.org/10.2527/2006.841145x>
- Zebiri, I., Abdel Samee, N., Alkanhel, R., Batra, H., & Hashim, F. A. (2024). Multiple phases modified termite life cycle optimizer for data clustering and engineering optimization. *Evolving Systems*, *16*(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12530-024-09645-x>

Zukowski, J., & Su, N.-Y. (2017). Survival of termites (Isoptera) exposed to various levels of relative humidity (RH) and water availability, and their RH preferences. *Florida Entomologist*, *100*(3), 532-538.